

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KONAN****FIRST NAME: KOUAME JEAN****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. How does Zotero help with citing sources in a document?

- By providing suggestions for citations.
- By automatically generating citations in various styles.¹**
- By sending reminder emails to include citations.
- By offering a template to write citations by hand.

2. What is the primary goal of qualitative research?

- To quantify and measure variables.
- To explore and understand complex phenomena.²**

¹ EUCLID, *Initial Student Orientation* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2022), 11-12.

²James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 41-44.

- To establish cause-and-effect relationships.
- To generalize findings to a larger population.

3. **What is the primary purpose of a literature review in a quantitative research paper?**

- To present the researcher's opinions.
- To provide background information and justify the research.³**
- To summarize the research findings.
- To criticize the work of other researchers.

4. **Which one is true regarding the Learning Management System (LMS) at EUCLID ?**

- The EUCLID LMS supports collaborative learning through features such as discussion forums, group assignments, and collaborative document editing tools that allow students to work together on projects.
- In the "Resources" section of the EUCLID LMS, students can typically find lecture notes, supplementary readings, multimedia content, and other educational materials related to their courses.
- The feature that allows students to access course materials, submit assignments, and engage in discussions is the "Course Dashboard" on the EUCLID LMS.

³ James P. Sampson, 41-44.

The primary purpose of the LMS at EUCLID is to facilitate online learning by providing a centralized platform for course materials, communication, and assessments.

All above.⁴

The "Gradebook" feature in the EUCLID LMS do not allows both students and instructors to track and monitor individual and overall class performance, displaying grades for assignments, quizzes, and exams.

5. What is a serious academic offense that students sometimes unintentionally commit when submitting papers?

Using a thesaurus excessively.

Including personal opinions.

Using direct quotes sparingly.

Paraphrasing without proper citation.⁵⁵

6. What is the primary purpose of including references in an academic research paper?

To showcase the author's knowledge.

To provide evidence for the claims made in the paper.⁶

To increase the word count of the paper.

⁴ EUCLID, *Initial Student Orientation* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2022), 11-12.

⁵Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 33-34.

⁶ Ibid, 12.

- To confuse the readers.

7. **When citing a journal article in the reference list, how should the title of the article be formatted according to the WHO style guide?**

- Upper Case.
- Title Case.
- Sentence case.
- Italics.**⁷

8. **Which of the following elements should be included in a Turabian-style bibliography entry for a book?**

- Author's name, title of the book, publication date.
- Author's name, title of the book, page numbers.
- Author's name, title of the book, publisher, and publication date.**⁸
- Author's name, title of the book, and city of publication.

9. **When citing a book in the bibliography, what information should be included ?**

- Book title, page number, publication date, author's name.
- Publisher, page number, author's name, book title.
- ISBN, author's name, book title, publication date.

⁷ World Health Organization, *WHO Editorial Style Manual* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 38.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2008), 242-261.

Author's name, book title, publication date, publisher.⁶⁹

10. In Turabian style, how should in-text citations be formatted for a direct quote?

[Author's name, page number].

(Author's name, page number).¹⁰

Author's name, page number.

Author's name (page number).

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 242-261.

¹⁰ Ibid, 242-261

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Bangui: EUCLID University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

World Health Organization. *WHO Editorial Style Manual*. Geneva: World Health Organization Press, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.